

Derivatization of Alcohols as S-(2-Benzoxoethyl) Thiuronium Xanthates

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A new procedure for the derivatization of alcohols as S-(2-benzoxoethyl) thiuronium xanthates has been described. Eight alcohols have been derivatized. The derivatives are obtained in good yield and are readily purified. The procedure is, therefore, recommended for the characterization of alcohols.

Alcohols can be derivatized as esters formed by the reaction with an acid chloride or anhydride, or as urethans formed by the reaction with an isocyanate. The derivatives commonly recommended are : 3,5-dinitrobenzoates^{2,3}, *p*-nitrobenzoates^{1,4}, phenylurethans^{5,6,7} and α -naphthyl urethans^{8,9} ; however, for the preparation of these derivatives it is desirable that the alcohol be anhydrous. Xanthates^{10,11}, have also been recommended for the characterization of primary and secondary alcohols but the derivatives in many cases do not have sharp m.p.'s. The authors have developed a convenient and valuable procedure for the derivatization of amines as benzylthiuronium dithiocarbamates¹². The derivatization of xanthates, obtained from alcohols, was similarly attempted, however, the use of S-(2-benzoxoethyl) thiuronium chloride¹³ which has been introduced as a superior reagent of this type was preferred to that of S-benzylthiuronium chloride. The characterization of the various available primary and secondary alcohols has been found to be conveniently possible.

The derivatives are stable and suitable for the characterization of alcohols. The yields of the derivatives are satisfactory and their purification is readily effected. The reactions involved are rapid and the reagents required are easily procurable in the pure form. The derivatization is possible even if the alcohol is not anhydrous because the alkyl xanthates form even in the presence of water. Thus, the procedure is valuable for the characterization of alcohols and is, therefore, recommended for this purpose. The detection and identification of alcohols is easily accomplished. Corrected m.p.'s of the derivatives and their analyses

have been recorded in Table 1. The sulphur and nitrogen content of the derivatives, as determined by Messenger's method and Dumas method respectively, agrees well with the calculated values.

TABLE 1

S-(2-Benzoxylethyl) thiuronium xanthates obtained from various alcohols

No.	Alcohol	Cor., m.p. of salt.	%sulphur		% Nitrogen	
			Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
1.	Methyl	86	28.94	29.54	8.42	8.58
2.	Ethyl	89	27.76	28.21	8.08	7.88
3.	<i>n</i> -Propyl	93	26.68	27.05	7.77	7.61
4.	<i>iso</i> -Propyl	98	.68	27.27	7.77	7.85
5.	<i>n</i> -Butyl	100	25.69	26.40	7.48	7.83
6.	<i>iso</i> -Butyl	103	25.69	25.98	7.48	7.75
7.	<i>iso</i> -Amyl	105	24.75	24.19	7.21	7.00
8.	Benzyl	82	23.55	24.00	6.85	7.34

In the case of ethylene glycol, the derivative was observed to undergo decomposition rapidly. The derivatization of tert-butanol, cyclohexanol, monoethanolamine, glycollic acid and lactic acid was found to be unsatisfactory.

EXPERIMENTAL

In a test tube, 1 ml. of alcohol and 2 pellets of potassium hydroxide were placed and warmed while shaking; when all the potassium hydroxide dissolved, the solution was cooled and 3 ml. of ether added. Then 1 ml. of carbon disulphide was added dropwise with shaking. The yellow precipitate of potassium alkyl xanthate was separated by decantation. The xanthate was then dissolved in minimum quantity of water. The pH of the solution was adjusted between 7 and 8 by the dropwise addition of *N* HCl in the beginning and 0.1*N* HCl towards the end, using phenolphthalein (in dioxane) as indicator. The pH was checked with universal pH paper (E. Merck). To the potassium xanthate solution thus obtained, aqueous solution of 1 g. of *S*-(2-benzoxylethyl) thiuronium chloride was added dropwise with shaking. *S*-(2-Benzoxylethyl) thiuronium xanthates were precipitated immediately in most cases, however, chilling was necessary in a few cases. The precipitate was filtered at the pump and rinsed with a little ether. To obtain the derivatives in analytically pure form one or two crystallizations from alcohol-ether mixture were necessary. The derivatives were dried in a vacuum desiccator and their m.p.'s were determined by the capillary tube method.

REFERENCES

1. D. W. Adamson and J. Kenner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 287.
2. W. M. D. Bryant, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 3758.
3. P. Sutter, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1938, **21**, 1266.
4. H. Henstock, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 216.

5. B. T. Dewey and N. F. Witt, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1942, **14**, 648.
6. B. Witten and E. E. Reid, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 2470.
7. E. Lambling, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1898, **19**, 771.
8. V. T. Bickel and H. E. French, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 747.
9. H. E. French and A. F. Wirtel, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 1736.
10. W. F. Whitmore and E. Lieber, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1935, **7**, 127.
11. I. S. Shupe, *J. Assoc. Offic. Agr. Chemists*, 1942, **25**, 495.
12. N. N. Singh and K. S. Boparai, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 1143.
13. Idem, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1971, **34**, 83.

